

Cultivars differed significantly in herbage yield at 90 DE, but not at the second cutting (Table 1). Mali Tawng, Pan Tawng, and Khao Puang Nak produced high herbage yields under drought stress, suggesting their potential for herbage production in deepwater areas that experience drought at the vegetative stage before flooding.

Mean grain yields were not significantly different and had no relationship to herbage yield. The relationship between grain yield differences and herbage yields was also low. The interaction between cultivars and herbage cutting was not significant, indicating a similar response to herbage cutting.

Mean grain yield of all cultivars with herbage cutting was significantly higher, a result mainly of more panicles/unit area. Spikelet number/panicle, fertility, and 1,000-grain weight were not affected by herbage cutting. Tiller number/unit area and harvest index increased significantly with herbage cutting but plant height and dry matter production at harvest decreased. Percentage of productive tillers and growth duration were not affected (Table 2).

Herbage cutting reduced plant height, but increased light transmission in the canopy, leading to higher tiller survival and, thus, to more panicles/unit area. That increased grain yield. ■

Table 2. Effect of herbage removal on agronomic characteristics of 20 deepwater rice cultivars. Huntra Rice Experiment Station, Ayutthaya, Thailand, 1989 WS.

Character	Control	Cut	Difference ^a
Grain yield (t/ha)	2.4	2.6	+ 0.20**
Panicles/m ²	103	117	+ 14**
Spikelets/panicle	120	116	- 4
Fertility (%)	87.7	86.9	- 0.88
1000-grain weight (g)	26.9	27.0	+ 0.06
Tillers/m ² at maturity	119	134	+ 15**
Productive tillers (%)	86	87	+ 1
Height (cm)	204	181	- 23**
Dry matter at harvest (t/ha)	12.3	10.3	- 2.01**
Harvest index	0.22	0.28	+ 0.06**
Duration (d)	232	232	± 0

^a** = significant at the 1% level.

Leaf venation in rice *Oryza sativa* L.

M. Shahid, A. Majid, M. Iqbal, T. Latif, M. J. Mirza, and F. A. Faiz, Breeding Section, Rice Research Institute, Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore, Pakistan

The relationship of leaf vein frequency and components of transport system is important to better understand the assimilate and its relationship to photo-

synthesis. There is a positive correlation between the ratio of mesophyll thickness to interveinal distance in the leaf and photosynthetic rate per unit area.

We studied rice leaf vein frequency after flowering on 20 varieties during 1987-88. Veins per unit area were counted on the flag leaf of the main culm of 30 plants/variety (10/replication).

Vein frequency ranged from 5.62/mm to 3.79/mm, with an average 4.70/mm (see table). Variety 4048-3 had the

highest vein frequency. The ratio of small vein to large vein also showed considerable differences among the varieties. The highest was 5.40 for Bas 370. ■

Small and large vein frequency ratio in 20 rice varieties. Lahore, Pakistan.

Variety	Mean vein frequency	Small vein		Large vein		Small vein: large vein ratio
		Mean	CV (%)	Mean	CV (%)	
4048-3	5.62	4.29	12.90	1.33	13.57	3.22
Bas 370	5.38	4.54	1.95	0.84	10.55	5.40
1053-1-2	5.32	3.90	9.07	1.33	13.60	2.99
4439	5.32	4.07	11.53	1.25	14.40	3.26
Bas 385	5.23	3.69	5.63	1.54	10.67	2.39
PK 3729-4	4.90	4.12	8.32	0.78	11.22	5.25
IR9	4.77	3.98	8.60	0.79	9.12	5.04
IR8	4.63	3.83	4.32	0.80	4.40	4.79
PK2480-7-3-1	4.60	3.79	4.73	0.81	16.80	4.68
PK3058-2-2-2	4.59	3.81	5.86	0.78	10.65	4.88
IR28	4.58	3.80	2.37	0.78	7.59	4.87
KS282	4.56	3.77	3.19	0.79	14.86	4.71
IR6	4.56	3.77	3.57	0.78	12.43	4.78
PK2001-1-5-5-1	4.55	3.77	3.96	0.78	11.37	4.83
IR64	4.52	3.75	12.77	0.77	8.47	4.87
PK3727-5	4.50	3.84	7.29	0.77	22.20	4.99
PK1385-9-1-B-1	4.34	3.55	8.32	0.79	13.13	4.49
PK3727-2	4.32	3.55	8.33	0.77	9.25	4.61
PK1385-9-1-B-12	4.02	3.25	11.10	0.77	4.73	4.22
PK1385-9-1-B-13	3.79	2.99	2.50	0.80	14.86	3.74
LSD values	0.14	0.12	0.10	at alpha 5%		

Simulation of yield potential of rice varieties in Cauvery delta zone, Tamil Nadu

M. N. Budhar, S. Palanisany, and A. A. Kareem, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai 612101, Tamil Nadu, India

We validated the ability of the L1D module of the MACROS simulation model developed at IRRI to predict the potential yield of rice varieties IR20, CO 43, and ADT38. The experiment was conducted in 1989 under irrigated conditions. Water, nutrients, and plant protection measures ensured that crop growth rate depended only on weather.

Experimental and simulated yields agreed more satisfactorily for local varieties CO 43 and ADT38 than for IR20 (see table). ■

Experimental and simulated grain yields of rice at TRRI, Aduthurai, India, 1989.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)		Agreement (%)
	Experimental	Simulated	
IR20	4.5	7.6	60
CO 43	5.3		6.5 81
ADT38	4.8		5.8 81